

*Paper Proposal for
OASE 126
Thinking through Models*

Title:

**Observations on Architectural Model-Making
—Corporate Environment *versus* Authorial Context**

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Abstract

Over recent decades, computer-aided design and other digital tools have contributed to a decline in haptic interaction and the relevance of architectural models. However, this shift didn't become exclusive enough for their extinction. Social media appears to have boosted a recent trend in which models —both old and new— have gained refreshed traction, admiration, and influence. As a result, models remain an integral part of exploration and representation, whether in large or small offices, and in authorial as well as corporate contexts. Nonetheless, the way they are used in such distinctive working structures is equally diverse. What are the points of overlap and divergence in the perception of models within corporate environments *versus* authorial contexts? Are they purely a method to convey an ethos?

This paper examines these differences through an empirical, first-hand account. Having worked in both types of architectural practices —such as SOM in New York, and Josep Lluís Mateo Arquitectes in Barcelona—, my relationship with models has undergone constant redefinition. Given the hierarchical and highly compartmentalized roles in large corporate offices, one might expect that hands-on involvement in inexpensive cardboard study model-making would not be accessible to a senior designer at his own desk. The fact that this was not entirely the case allows for a deeper examination of the role models play in different settings and geographies. Depending on context, they can be produced as depiction artifacts, sculptural objects to be contemplated; or —as it will be largely explored in this text— as functional devices to be dismantled, modified, and transformed, without a predetermined goal of completion. They can be built realistically to showcase structural achievements or conceptually to crystallize an architectural reasoning. Models can, it seems, be more than mere processes of tridimensional investigation or illustration; they can also serve as means of cultural, technical, and intellectual affirmation.

Keywords: *architectural models; corporate versus authorial; haptic function*
